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THE VALUE AND ASPECTS OF THE RIGHT TO A FAIR TRIAL FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF LEGAL SECURITY¹

The study is dedicated to the right to a fair trial, with the aim of highlighting the necessity of researching and understanding its essence, dimensions, and content to successfully strengthen the internal legal mechanism for its enforcement and protection, as a factor ensuring legal security. A distinct emphasis is placed on the need to distinguish the content and interpretation of this right by the Strasbourg Court from its understanding and the mechanism of its protection, assurance, and enforcement at the state level. To this end, the national and international legal regulations are presented, and the semantics of such terms as “equity”, “fair justice”, “fair trial” and “principle of equity” are clarified.

Keywords: justice, judicial process, equity, fair justice, the principle of equity, fair trial, right to a fair trial, rights and guarantees, legal security.

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VALOAREA ȘI ASPECTELE DREPTULUI LA UN PROCES ECHITABIL DIN PERSPECTIVA SECURITĂȚII JURIDICE

Studiul este dedicat dreptului la un proces echitabil, cu scopul de a evidenția necesitatea cercetării și înțelegerii esenței, dimensiunilor și conținutului acestuia în vederea consolidării cu succes a mecanismului juridic intern de aplicare și protecție a acestuia, ca factor de asigurare a securității juridice. Un accent distinct este pus pe necesitatea de a distinge conținutul și interpretarea acestui drept de către Curtea de la Strasbourg de înțelegerea sa și mecanismul de protecție, asigurare și executare a acestuia la nivel de stat. În acest scop, sunt prezentate reglementările legale naționale și internaționale și se clarifică semantica unor termeni precum „echitate”, „justiție echitabilă”, „proces echitabil” și „principiul echității”.

Cuvinte-cheie: justiție, proces judiciar, echitate, justiție corectă, principiul echității, proces echitabil, dreptul la un proces echitabil, drepturi și garanții, securitate juridică.

1. INTRODUCTION

This study is dedicated to a highly relevant topic for our society, which, unfortunately, although doctrinally addressed, lacks adequate regulation and is often overlooked in judicial practice [1, p. 65]. It concerns *the right to a fair trial*, a right guaranteed by the *European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms* [2] (ECHR) and highly valued by the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), as it is fundamental for litigants and represents a supreme value in a state governed by the rule of law.

As is well known, the Republic of Moldova frequently loses before the Strasbourg Court, primarily due to violations of the *right to a fair trial*. Therefore, it is only logical to ask: what measures has the state taken to prevent, identify, and remedy violations of the *right to a fair trial* at the domestic level? Such measures are necessary not only to avoid losing cases before the ECHR, but also to prevent the “financial losses” associated with these cases, and, last but not least, to strengthen the quality of justice and the credibility of the judiciary. The situation regarding the enforcement of the *right to a fair trial* directly reflects the democratic and legal values of our state, which must be based on fair, high-quality, and equitable justice.

In an attempt to answer the question posed above, we find it necessary to clarify several relevant aspects gradually, namely: the scope of the *right to a fair trial* (in other words, it’s content); how it is regulated at the national level; how its practical implementation is ensured and safeguarded; the risks associated with violations of this right; when and how violations or non-compliance can be prevented, identified, and remedied at the national level.

Obviously, addressing these aspects requires more than a single study. Therefore, to respect the limitations of this volume, this scientific endeavour will focus on the normative regulation of *the right to a fair trial*, as well as on the analysis of the essence and the relationship between concepts such as “equity”, “the principle of equity” and “fair trial”, with the ultimate goal of outlining the content of the right in question. We reserve the option of addressing other equally important aspects tangentially or in greater depth in future research.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

In conducting this study, several theoretical (classical) research methods were employed, including the following: *the logical method* (which encompasses components such as abstraction, analysis [both deductive and inductive], and synthesis), *the comparative method* (primarily used to analyze the content of the right to a fair trial as outlined by the international normative framework in comparison with its national legal counterpart), and *the systemic method* (employed for analyzing and interpreting the current legal framework).

3. MAIN CONTENT OF THE RESEARCH

Regulation of the Right to a Fair Trial. At the international level, the *right to a fair trial* is primarily enshrined in the following key instruments:

Universal Declaration of Human Rights [3]: Article 10 – “Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.” Article 11, paragraph 1 – “Everyone charged with a penal offence has the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defence”;

European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms [2]: Article 6 – “1. In the determination of his civil rights and obligations or of any criminal charge against him, everyone is entitled to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial tribunal established by law. Judgment shall be pronounced publicly but the press and public may be excluded from all or part of the trial in the interests of morals, public order or national security in a democratic society, where the interests of juveniles or the protection of the private life of the parties so require, or to the extent strictly necessary in the opinion of the court in special circumstances where publicity would prejudice the interests of justice. 2. Everyone charged with a criminal offence shall be presumed innocent until proven guilty according to law. (...)”;

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights [4]: Article 14 – “1. All persons shall be equal before the courts and tribunals. In the determination of any criminal charge against him, or of his rights and obligations in a suit at law, everyone shall be entitled to a fair and public hearing by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal established by law. The press and the public may be excluded from all or part of a trial for reasons of morals, public order (order public) or national security in a democratic society, or when the interest of the private lives of the parties so requires, or to the extent strictly necessary in the opinion of the court in special circumstances where publicity would prejudice the interests of justice; but any judgement rendered in a criminal case or in a suit at law shall be made public except where the interest of juvenile persons otherwise requires or the proceedings concern matrimonial disputes or the guardianship of children. 2. Everyone charged with a criminal offence shall have the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law. (...)”;

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [5]: Article 47 – “Everyone whose rights and freedoms guaranteed by the law of the Union are violated has the right to an effective remedy before a tribunal in compliance with the conditions laid down in this Article. Everyone is entitled to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time by

an independent and impartial tribunal previously established by law. Everyone shall have the possibility of being advised, defended and represented. Legal aid shall be made available to those who lack sufficient resources in so far as such aid is necessary to ensure effective access to justice.” Article 48 – “(1) Everyone who has been charged shall be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law. (2) Respect for the rights of the defence of anyone who has been charged shall be guaranteed.”

As outlined above, *the right to a fair trial* was initially enshrined in explicit terms in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and subsequently incorporated, largely in its original form, into major international instruments, including the *European Convention on Human Rights*, the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*, and the *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*. While these international instruments do not offer a comprehensive definition of *the right to a fair trial*, they delineate broad guarantees for its protection, along with specific safeguards in the context of criminal proceedings. Consequently, the responsibility of defining and elaborating the content of *the right to a fair trial* has primarily fallen to judicial interpretations (particularly those of the European Court of Human Rights), as well as to legal doctrine [1, p. 66].

Regarding the domestic regulation of the right in question, it is important to note that, at the constitutional level, the Republic of Moldova does not provide an explicit enshrinement of this right. However, according to some voices [6, p. 156], certain elements of this right can be found in various provisions of the *Constitution of the Republic of Moldova* [7], including Article 20 (Access to Justice), Article 52 (Right to Petition), Article 53 (Right of an Individual Harmed by a Public Authority), and Articles 114-119 (related to the judicial authority).

In this regard, researchers observe [8, p. 10]: “The Constitution does not explicitly regulate *the right to a fair trial*, but such a right can be inferred from the systematic interpretation of constitutional provisions,” which establish the following: “Everyone has the right to effective redress before competent courts against acts that violate their rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests” (Article 20, paragraph 1); “Justice is administered by the Supreme Court of Justice, appellate courts, and judges. (2) Specialized courts may be established for certain types of cases, in accordance with the law. (3) The establishment of extraordinary courts is prohibited” (Article 115); “Judges are independent and subject only to the law, and they are irremovable” (Article 116, paragraph 1); “Court hearings are public. Closed hearings are permitted only in cases established by law, in compliance with all procedural rules” (Article 117); “Against judicial decisions, interested parties and competent state bodies may exercise remedies in accordance with the law” (Article 119).

These are regarded as the “constitutionally guaranteed minimum conditions for a fair trial, conditions that must be supplemented by provisions of the organic law concerning the organization and functioning of the judicial courts” [8, p. 10], as well as by procedural legislation.

In comparative terms, the *Constitution of Romania* [9], explicitly incorporates the text of Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) in Article 21, paragraph (3), stating: “Parties have the right to a fair trial and to the resolution of their cases within a reasonable time”. According to experts, the cited constitutional provision (revised in 2003) represents “an accurate reception of modern legal developments at the European level and an alignment of the legal protection of subjective rights through do-

mestic regulations with international standards” [10, p. 61]. Moreover, it is emphasized that “unlike the ECHR, which conditions the applicability of Article 6 on the existence of a complaint concerning civil rights and obligations or a criminal charge, Article 21 of the Romanian Constitution does not impose such limitations, meaning that, by applying the provisions of Article 20 of the Constitution, the guarantees of the *right to a fair trial* will extend to all disputes, regardless of their nature” [11, p. 163].

This opinion merits attention because it introduces a significant idea: the distinction between the content and interpretation of *the right to a fair trial* at the level of the Strasbourg Court and its content/interpretation at the national level. From this perspective, the need to delineate and clarify the content of this right, beyond the interpretations and applications provided by the European Court, becomes apparent. To some extent, this issue will also be addressed in the following sections.

In addition to the positive aspects mentioned, it is important to note that the Constitution of Romania, like the international acts referenced above, does not explicitly define *the right to a fair trial* nor does it provide detailed guarantees for its protection, making only a specific reference to the guarantee of a reasonable duration of proceedings [11, p. 157]. Nevertheless, researchers correctly argue that “under Article 20¹ of the Constitution of Romania, in defining the fair trial guaranteed by Article 21, all the express and implicit guarantees of a fair trial as provided by Article 6 of the ECHR and interpreted in the case law of the Strasbourg Court are applicable” [11, p. 157].

Returning to the situation in the Republic of Moldova, we maintain that it is essential for the Constitution to explicitly enshrine *the right to a fair trial*, elevating it to the status of a fundamental right and constitutional principle. This would carry all the legal consequences associated with such a status, including the constitutional obligation of the state to guarantee, ensure, and effectively protect this right in practice [1, p. 66].

In contrast to the Constitution, *the right to a fair trial* is explicitly regulated within procedural legislation, as follows:

The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova [12]: “Any person has the right to have their case examined and resolved fairly, within a reasonable time, by an independent, impartial, legally established court, which will act in accordance with the Criminal Procedure Code” (Art. 19 – “Access to Justice”). Moreover, elements of this right are also reflected in other provisions of the Code, such as Article 20, which regulates the principle of conducting criminal proceedings within reasonable terms, explicitly incorporating conditions derived from the jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR).

The Contravention Code of the Republic of Moldova [13] stipulates in Article 381, paragraph (2) (“Access to justice”): “Any person has the right to have their case examined and resolved fairly, within a reasonable time, by an independent, impartial, legally constituted court, which acts in accordance with this Code.” Furthermore, Article 374, paragraph (3)

¹ Specifically, Article 20 of the Constitution of Romania provides: “(1) The constitutional provisions regarding the rights and freedoms of citizens will be interpreted and applied in accordance with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the international covenants, and other treaties to which Romania is a party. (2) In case of discrepancies between the covenants and treaties concerning fundamental human rights, to which Romania is a party, and domestic laws, international regulations shall take precedence, unless the Constitution or domestic laws contain more favorable provisions.”

of the Code provides: “The contravention process is conducted based on the general principles of contravention law, in accordance with the Constitution, this Code, the Criminal Procedure Code in cases expressly provided for by this Code, as the norms of international law and international treaties concerning human rights and fundamental freedoms to which the Republic of Moldova is a party.” This provision indicates that *the right to a fair trial* is guaranteed in contravention proceedings through the provisions of the Contravention Code, the Criminal Procedure Code, and applicable international instruments [14, p. 483].

The Administrative Code of the Republic of Moldova [15] establishes in Article 38, paragraph (2): “Any person has the right to have their case heard fairly, within a reasonable time, by an independent, impartial court established by law. To this end, the court is required to take all measures permitted by law to ensure the prompt conduct of the proceedings.”

In contrast with the aforementioned codes, the *Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova* [16], which is of particular interest to our study, does not contain explicit provisions establishing *the right to a fair trial*. Instead, the Code outlines several principles that implicitly reflect aspects of this right, including: the administration of justice only in court /Art. 19/; the independence of judges, who are subjects only to the law /Art. 20/; equality before the law and justice /Art. 22/; the public nature of judicial hearings /Art. 23/; the language of proceedings and the right to an interpreter /Art. 24/; the adversarial nature of the process, along with the equality of the parties in procedural rights /art. 26/) [1, p. 66].

By comparing the provisions of the cited codes, researchers conclude that “the formula employed by the legislator in these codes to establish *the right to a fair trial* (except the *Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova*) does not fully reflect the entirety of this right, as outlined by legal doctrine and the jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights. Many elements of this right are regulated separately in various articles of the cited codes, which complicates the clear delineation and specification of its exact content. Consequently, it is far more justifiable to recognize *the right to a fair trial* as a general principle of judicial proceedings, one that entails the guarantee of all procedural rights of the participants, intending to ensure a just and equitable resolution of the cases brought before the court” [14, p. 483]. In this context, researchers [17, p. 310] advocate for “the necessity of expressly regulating *the right to a fair trial* as a fundamental principle, both at the constitutional level and across all procedural laws,” asserting that “only under these conditions will the state be able to guarantee the respect of this right to all litigants at the national level, thus strengthening the foundations of the rule of law.

In essence, we consider the idea to be valid; however, if viewed in this way, the principle in question would largely overlap with the *principle of legality* in judicial proceedings and, as a result, would lose much of its significance. Therefore, we believe that, in addition to the normative enshrinement of *the right to a fair trial* as a constitutional principle, it is absolutely necessary to recognize it as a subjective procedural right, accompanied by a concrete mechanism for its guarantee and protection [1, p. 67]. Some arguments to support this position are outlined below.

Semantic clarifications: “equity”, “fair justice”, “principle of equity” and “fair trial”. Before directly addressing the definition and content of *the right to a fair trial*, it

is necessary, firstly, to clarify the semantic nuances of expressions such as “equity”, “fair justice”, “principle of equity” and “fair trial”. This clarification will contribute to a more precise understanding of the right in question.

According to the Explanatory Dictionary of the Romanian Language, the word “echitabil” (“fair”) is defined as “based on justice, on truth, fair, just, impartial” [18, p. 105].

In legal doctrine, *equity* is considered “a principle that underpins any legal system” [19, p. 89], in other words, a fundamental principle. This implies that “equity pertains both to the legislative process (the work of the legislator) and to the application and interpretation of the law” [20, p. 182; 21, p. 92]. More specifically, it is argued that the *principle of equity*, as a fundamental principle of law, requires “the legislator’s restraint in defining rights and obligations during the lawmaking process, as well as the impartiality of the authorities tasked with applying the law” [22, p. 208].

Certainly, we support this position, and it is essential to emphasize that, in addition to ensuring the equity of the law and the process of its enforcement, it is equally crucial to guarantee the fairness of the procedures through which unlawful behaviour is sanctioned or legal disputes are resolved – specifically, judicial procedures.

From the perspective of the subject at hand, particular attention must be given to the judicial activity of the courts, as an essential function of applying the law, entrusted with one of the most important responsibilities in society – the administration of justice.

In an effort to underscore the inseparable link between *equity* and *justice*, we draw attention to the provisions of Article 4 of the *Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova*, which, in the section on the duties of civil proceedings, establishes the “fair judgment of cases within a reasonable time, concerning the protection of violated or disputed rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of natural and legal persons (...)”. This provision makes it clear that the primary objective of civil judicial proceedings is the *fair (just, impartial)*, that is, *equitable*, resolution of cases brought before the court. It follows that *justice* itself must be *equitable*, otherwise, it would fail to qualify as *justice*.

Even though *equity* is an inherent characteristic of *justice*, both legal doctrine and judicial practice (particularly that of the European Court) acknowledge the possibility of achieving *inequitable justice*. In this regard, it has been correctly argued that “the right of access to justice cannot serve as a sufficient constitutional guarantee of all fundamental rights and freedoms if *justice* itself is *not equitable*” [8, p. 10]. Consequently, we observe the existence of a *presumption of justice’s equitable nature*, which may, however, be rebutted.

The presumption is grounded in the fact that “for the *fair* adjudication of cases (civil cases), the entire procedural framework (civil procedure) is established, outlining all the procedural guarantees necessary for *equity*” [23, p. 41]. Consequently, *fair justice* is understood as justice administered under the conditions explicitly prescribed by law, primarily in the form of the rights and obligations of the parties involved in the proceedings, as well as those of the court.

Concerning the *principle of equity* in the administration of justice, it is argued that “it encompasses two components: ensuring the highest level of guarantees regarding the administration of justice and applying the fundamental principles of law, constitutional principles, as well as the international treaties ratified by the state (which, in turn, form part of domestic law), particularly when the resolution of the case necessitates going be-

yond what is prescribed by the law” [10, p. 49].

From a comparative perspective, English law is of particular interest in this regard, as *equity* is recognized as a “source of law” [24, p. 16]. In contrast, American law defines the *jurisdiction of equity* as “the authority of a court to administer justice when no specific law exists that governs the case brought before it” [25, p. 198].

From the opinions presented, it can be concluded that the *principle of equity* holds a distinct meaning in relation to *fair justice*. It is understood as an inherent standard or benchmark within the field of justice, necessitating the administration of justice in accordance with the fundamental principles of law (as outlined in constitutional legislation and the international normative framework). In this regard, the *principle of equity* is only applicable primarily in cases where the administration of justice requires the use of analogy (both of law and rights), a possibility explicitly recognized for judges (with certain exceptions) under Article 12, paragraph (3) of the *Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova*.

Consequently, we can deduce that *justice is fair* when it leads to the just resolution of a case grounded in the provisions of applicable law (both substantive and procedural), or, where necessary, in accordance with the *principle of equity*. At the same time, we assert that no case can be considered justly or fairly resolved if the process fails to respect the law (both substantive and procedural) or, where applicable, the fundamental principles of law (including the *principle of equity*).

In addition to the points already discussed, we deem it important to clarify that the *principle of equity* should not be conflated with the *principle of a fair trial*, as their contents are distinct. To differentiate between the two, it is first necessary to define the concept of a “*fair trial*.”

In the prevailing opinion, the concept is understood either as a “judicial process conducted in accordance with legal provisions and fundamental principles”, or as a “judicial process conducted with respect to the procedural rights and obligations of the participants as prescribed by law”. Based on the understanding of *fair justice* (outlined above), we align with the second interpretation, as we believe that a *fair trial* constitutes an integral aspect of *fair justice*. It represents an essential component in its procedural dimension and serves as a relevant indicator of the overall fairness of the process.

This position is implicitly supported in legal doctrine, where it is emphasized that “the most important procedural rights of litigants have been consolidated into a system of judicial guarantees for the realization of justice, under the term *fair trial* or, more recently, *the right to a fair trial*” [10, p. 51].

Consequently, we deduce that the *principle of fairness of the trial process* differs from the *principle of equity* in that the former seeks to guarantee the observance of all judicial safeguards (the procedural rights of litigants) in the administration of justice. In contrast, the *principle of equity* ensures the possibility of administering justice in cases where the law does not provide a specific solution.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From the analysis presented above, one key uncertainty emerges regarding the roles of *equity* within the judicial process as a whole. While procedural law (specifically the *Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova*) recognizes *equity* as a goal of any trial

(namely, the „fair/equitable resolution of cases”), both case law and legal doctrine elevate it to the status of a principle and a subjective right. Based on the axiom that „justice is only equitable”, we argue that the identified uncertainty can be addressed by considering two distinct aspects of the *fair process*: *equity* as a principle and *equity* as a subjective right.

In this context, one might question why there is still a need for *the right to a fair trial* when the *principle of fairness in the process* is already recognized. The answer is undoubtedly affirmative: such a need exists because the recognition of *the right to a fair trial* grants litigants a subjective right (enshrined in law), which must be defined with concrete content and be practically applicable in situations where it is violated. In other words, litigants can challenge and demand the observance of certain procedural principles (including the *principle of fairness in the trial*) only when their subjective rights have been infringed upon.

Thus, while the *principle of fairness in the judicial process* serves primarily as a standard or benchmark for the courts, *the right to a fair trial* functions as a specific tool granted to litigants, enabling them to enforce *fairness* (i.e., the observance of the *principle of fairness*) in the administration of justice. The key issue, however, lies in how litigants can effectively exercise this right at the national level. To answer this question, it is essential, firstly, to delineate the precise content of *the right to a fair trial* (a task we intend to address in a subsequent scientific endeavour).

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